

The HuT

Outreach and Engagement Activities

Deliverable D6.2

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, T6.2 Outreach and Engagement

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Version 1.0

(25 July 2024)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101073957

1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
Project Title	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
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Project Duration	October 2022 – September 2026 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D6.2
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP6 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Task	T6.2 – Outreach and Engagement
Lead beneficiary	MET
Contributing beneficiary/ies	ICONS

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	13.07.2024	Joanne Robbins (MET) Ilaria Bonetti (ICONS) Eylul Aksekili (ICONS)	First draft
0.2	17.07.2024	Glauco Gallotti, Francesco Lo Conti (LEITHA)	Critical review and proofreading
0.3	19.07.2024	Joanne Robbins (MET) Ilaria Bonetti (ICONS) Eylul Aksekili (ICONS)	Edits for approval
1.0	25.07.2024	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Proofreading, final version

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3. Introduction

The HuT project looks to address the possible impacts of extreme weather and climate events and identify solutions and strategies across sectoral silos. It is taking a trans-disciplinary and all-hazards approach to enable the adoption of multi-hazard disaster risk reduction (DRR) solutions. The complexity of adopting such an approach means that the project needs to leverage expertise from a wide range of disciplines, existing global and regional networks as well as share its learnings from different adoption strategies. This requires both internal (to the project) and external outreach and engagement.

Work package 6 has a core objective to support optimal conditions and solutions for the long-term sustainability of the project. To this goal, the project aims to disseminate its achievements and learnings, share good practices and develop guidance leveraging internationally recognized networks and peer-to-peer engagement across 10 demonstrators, i.e., WP1 Demonstrators' arena.

Task 6.2 is focused on outreach and engagement. It aims to facilitate the delivery of science content through the project's channels, website and social media, set up in T6.1, by drawing together outputs, experiences and solutions from within and external to the project. Project progress is regularly collated and shared via website updates, a regular newsletter, and other outlets (e.g., PreventionWeb). To promote good practices, the use of the Local DRR nexus Forums is encouraged by means of specific initiatives (e.g., topic discussions, invited contributions).

Outreach and Engagement activities are carried out across multiple scales (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Multi-layered communication strategy which draws together local stakeholder engagement and demonstrator-level innovations (left), through a Consortium Communication Hub (centre) and is extended out to leverage expertise across a range of international networks (right). [HB = Human Behaviour; G&P = Governance and Policy; S&T = Science and Technology.

The different outreach and engagement scales are described as: local, consortium and global. Local scale represents the within-demonstrator activities (e.g. local-level engagement with demonstrator-specific stakeholders). Consortium scale represents engagement across the wider project (e.g. cross-demonstrator knowledge sharing). Global scale represents our reach to external networks and science communities. Strategies for outreach and engagement are different at each scale. The following sections describe the strategies and progress the project has made with outreach and engagement across these different scales, starting with global and working backwards to the local scale.

4. Global outreach and engagement activities

4.1. The HuT project website

As The HuT Project has matured, it has been increasingly growing its online presence. The HuT project website (<https://thehut-nexus.eu/>) was set up in May 2023 and aims to be a launch-pad for individuals interested in knowing more about the project, its scope and activities. It is also a means of sharing content, including deliverable reports, news and subject-specific content. A video outlining the project's purpose is accessible via the webpage and The HuT Nexus YouTube channel. There are also descriptions of the 10 demonstrators (DEMs) across which the project is working. These represent test sites for trialing and assessing new ways to limit/manage risks associated with weather and climate extremes and bring together representatives from different disciplines within a more localized context. This enables a better understand of the unique challenges an area may face in addressing the climate change challenge, while also enabling cross-fertilization and the identification of scalable and transferable solutions. Although the project is taking an “all-hazards” approach, not all demonstrators are engaging across all hazards being considered. The descriptions of the different demonstrators outline the focus hazards for each demonstrator and the needs that they are trying to address. These high-level descriptions are not only useful for encouraging awareness and ensuring internal project linkages but are also useful for external projects (local or international), who may be working on similar topics and wish to connect with a specific demonstrator.

Since the launch of the project website, the total pageviews generated is **12,988**. In parallel with our outreach efforts, we have achieved **5,803** engagements. This means that 5,803 users interacted with and responded to our content on the project website.

The **Website Engagement Index (WEI) is 81**. The WEI indicates the number of page views lasting more than 60 seconds out of 100 page views. A WEI of 80 means that 80 out of 100 page views lasted more than 60 seconds. A high WEI translates to high engagement on the website. The 60-second measure has been defined as the minimum time to claim that content has generated interest. Figure 2 below represents the time spent by each user on the website. Since the launch of The HuT, the peak engagement has coincided with the completion of our social media campaigns. Therefore, our future actions to generate more engagement will be aligned with this data.

Figure 2: Time users spent on the website shown by month, starting in December 2022.

4.2. Editorial Products

A total of 29 editorial products have been produced and shared via the website. These are: 1 Article, 14 news releases, 1 newsletter, 1 press release and 12 project updates. Project resources are also shared on the website, including deliverable reports (20 currently accessible from the Resources space). The website has been viewed 12,998 times since its inception. In addition to the external outreach, the project is keen to facilitate the sharing of information among partners, and therefore a “Partners area” has been created within the website with restricted access. In this area, the partners can find the project’s documents’ folders and a logbook which collects monthly updates from the partners and the DEMs (this area is directly managed by the coordinator).

The editorial contents’ outreach is monitored regularly thus allowing to fine-tune the communication materials’ contents, to gain more impact over time.

Figure 3 shows The HuT publications’ effectiveness per type as of June 2024.

Figure 3: The HuT Projects publication effectiveness by quadrants of different publication type.

The article has shown great effectiveness with both outreach and engagement above the average.

The other formats have displayed an average effectiveness with a good performance of project update and paper format which have neutral values in terms of outreach (views) and engagement (reactions). Meaning that they did not perform as well as the video, but they had good outreach.

From this graph, we can assume that The Hut community is interested in video format which usually communicates specific contents and project progresses. Given the publication format results, we will consider privileging this kind of contents in the upcoming months.

The **Public Effectiveness Index (PEI) is 28**. The PEI is measured by dividing the engagement to outreach and describes the interest generated by the publications related to the project.

4.3. Social Media Channels

The project recognizes that inclusive outreach needs to be supported by a range of dissemination mechanisms. We have therefore adopted a multi-channel outreach approach, where outputs from the project are shared across multiple platforms. The HuT social media channels, X and LinkedIn, have been created to promote the project, its objectives and its results. These social channels have been used to promote the main events related to the project and communicate major initiatives implemented by the partners.

Figure 4: Examples of HuT project posts published on LinkedIn (left) and X (right).

Three social media campaigns have been launched, respectively for the International Day of Women in Science (#MyDearLittleScientist), The HuT DEMs presentation and #MitigationWords (in collaboration with [Distender project](#)). Table 1 provides an overview of analytics for our core channels (LinkedIn and X).

The **Social Media Index (SEI) is 55**. The social media engagement index (SEI) is measured by dividing the engagement to outreach and describes the interest generated by social media channels. Since the launch of the social media channels a total of 315 have been generated.

The outreach and the engagement of the content produced is shown in Figure 5, the social media engagement trend is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Analytics data for the HuT Projects core dissemination channels as of July 2024.

Figure 6: Social media engagement trend from October 2022 to June 2024.

4.4. Networking & Outreach

Networking is a related form of outreach and engagement, and the project has actively engaged with several ongoing European projects. More details of networking activities are provided in the D6.3 report, including a list of projects with whom The HuT is in close contact. In the context of outreach and engagement, a traditional avenue for science communities is the sharing of knowledge and learning through conference attendance and peer-reviewed publications. Table 1 provides a list of conference attendance, where presentations on The HuT and its outputs were given. Training events where knowledge to/from The HuT project were shared are also shown.

Table 1: Presentations at national and international conferences and The HuT led international training events (in reverse chronological order).

Name (period)	Type	Target audience	Short description
Presentations at conference (June, 2024)	Conferences	Research communities	Two presentations on multi-hazard warning systems at the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World, Amsterdam (Netherlands)
Presentations at EGU Conference (April 2024)	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation and Poster showcasing results from Dem 1 (Valencia) and Dem 8 (Ogliastro)

Presentation at National Urban Water Management Conference (April 2024)	Conferences	Research Communities	Presentation on mobile application and future plans being delivered under Dem 7 (Tisza)
Organization of webinar (July 2023)	Education and training events	Specific end user communities; International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.); Civil society	Online webinar "Translating Warnings into Actions: Improving Early Warning Systems to Protect Communities"
Presentations at EGU conference (June, 2023)	Conferences	Research communities	Project results presented in many different sessions of the European Geosciences Union (EGU) general assembly 2023, Vienna (Austria)
Presentation in Conference (June 2023)	Conferences	Research communities; Specific end user communities	Conference "Climate crisis and systemic risks: Lessons Learned from COVID-19", Herrenhausen (Germany)
Organization of session in conference (June 2023)	Conferences	Research communities; Specific end user communities; Civil society	Science-art collaboration session "Staging Early Warning System stories" organized at the European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) in Dublin (Ireland)

Content from these engagements is shared with project consortium members from all the demonstrators via a logbook but are also sign-posted externally across all social media channels used by The HuT project where it is appropriate to do so.

5. Consortium outreach and engagement activities

At the consortium scale issues, challenges, progress and results from the demonstrators are being gathered, together with experience and good practice from several external networks and shared among and between the demonstrators. As highlighted in the previous section, our routine exchange media is primarily via the project website and our social media channels. However, specific additional content will also provide a means of engaging both the internal project community and the broader DRR community. We therefore plan to produce a regular newsletter (8 issues), together with cross-project meetings (working groups), fact sheets (>8), short video interviews or video clips (>15) and presentations. Interaction across demonstrators and experiences from both within the consortium and the wider international community will be shared through a knowledge repository, which will be part of the International DRR nexus Forum. These strategies will enhance information sharing and ensure efficiency across The HuT by enabling the expertise of the leading European institutions to be accessible to all demonstrators. This will support cross-fertilization and collaboration across demonstrators, hazards, and the nexus.

5.1. Newsletters

The HuT Project will be sharing progress, results and event updates via a project newsletter. The newsletter's audience is both internal (to the HuT Project) and external. We will issue 8 of these throughout the life of the project. Our first newsletter was made available online (via the website) in March 2024 (<https://thehut-nexus.eu/category/newsletter/>). The topics covered included: (1) updates from The HuT General Assembly 2023; (2) Work undertaken on the topic of 'Science-Art-Society' and (3) an overview of a topical, aligned event (the conference on "[Creating Effective Warnings for All](#)"). We also provide an update on The HuT project outputs, recent and upcoming events and specific cross-demonstrator/cross-work package opportunities for interaction (e.g. Working Groups). 134 people received the first newsletter. To keep up to date with The HuT project activities, we invite people to subscribe to future newsletters. We currently have 173 people subscribed. Content for the second The HuT Newsletter is being planned presently, with an anticipated future release in early autumn 2024.

5.2. Cross-Theme Working Groups

Recognizing that The HuT project is covering a significant breadth of research, it was decided that cross-cutting working groups would support closer collaboration between demonstrators, enable knowledge sharing on cross-cutting themes and support transferability of methods and solutions beyond a single demonstrator (a core aim of the project). With this in mind, two working groups have been set up to promote cross-demonstrator knowledge exchange. These working groups aim to be spaces where project members can discuss issues and challenges related to specific topics that are perhaps limiting their ability to accelerate specific activities (e.g., improving forecasts for early warning systems). The working groups are envisaged to be a safe space to enable upskilling, where that may be needed or requested, and to provide support from experts when critical issues arise. These experts may be internal (i.e., already part of The HuT project) or they may be external. The facilitation of external SME's and the sharing of existing science research within these working groups is aimed to ensure that all demonstrators can accelerate

progression a range of activities, leveraging the collective expertise within the consortium and their wider network.

The Weather and Climate Working Group had its first meeting in February 2024. At that initial meeting we discussed the purpose of the working group and identified some initial topics of discussions that were pertinent to those in attendance (e.g. impacts of the weather; early warning systems; use of meteorological data). We had representation from several demonstrators covering regions in the UK, Italy, Spain, Hungary and Switzerland. The hazards of interest ranged from floods and landslides, through to heatwaves and droughts. The group agreed to meet every two months and to have a flexible and organic structure. The participants were encouraged to suggest topics and challenges that they would like to discuss and share with the group. It is envisaged that the WG will operate throughout the life of The HuT project as needed and therefore will be able to cover a variety of topics over time. To streamline discussions and to enable people to prepare ahead of the meetings, we have decided to orientate discussions around the Warning Value Chain capabilities (Figure 2). Our second meeting (May 2024) was therefore focused on Hydrometeorological observation data that might be used in relation to the above-mentioned hazards. The third meeting, scheduled for July 2024, will focus on forecast datasets and the representation of uncertainty. All meetings are recorded and are made available in the consortium google drive repository.

Figure 7: A schematic of the warning value chain (from the WMO HIWeather Value Chain Flagship project) showing the capabilities and outputs (green mountains) and information exchanges (bridges) linking the capabilities and their associated communities.

The second project Working Group to be established is the Real-time monitoring and IoT-based warning group. This had its first meeting in March 2024 and has similar aims to the Weather and Climate Working Group but is also engaging closely with the [LandAware – the international network on Landslide Early Warning Systems](#) (working group 8). The group will discuss IoT (Internet of Things) where a network of sensors can gather and share information in real-time enabling analysis, automation and enhanced control over physical systems. The group has identified 5 objectives of the working group:

- (1) Informing and sharing information and knowledge on IoT-based monitoring and warning among The HuT partners.

- (2) Learning and staying informed about what's happening outside of the HuT project.
- (3) Being informed about IoT-based monitoring and warning case studies and initiatives.
- (4) Creating a monitoring and warning catalogue of sites providing real-time monitoring and IoT-based warning, making the dataset available (but not in real-time).
- (5) Addressing other tasks suggested by the working groups participants and the wider project consortium.

In May 2024, the Real-time monitoring and IoT-based warning Working Group engaged in a joint workshop with LandAware Working Group 8. This joint workshop was organized to support objective 4 listed above. The workshop was 1.5 hours long and included presentations from 3 of the HuT project demonstrators covering: (1) monitoring and modelling of floods and landslides; (2) operational landslide forecasting at local and regional scale and (3) IoT technologies for sensing systems.

5.3. Fact Sheets

The HuT Project aims to produce at least 8 fact sheets during the life of the project. The intended audiences of these outputs are the consortium research community, as well as the broader external research and practitioner communities involved in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). Fact sheet content aims to be short, concise descriptions of the challenges and solutions around a specific topic of interest to the project. We endeavor for these fact sheets to have wide appeal and therefore link to challenges being faced within the wider, global DRR community.

We are using Trello (an online project management tool) to track progress and delivery of our external outreach products. The development process for the fact sheets will be replicated for each new production. This includes: (1) the identification of a content theme and within-project subject matter experts (SMEs); (2) develop content using the fact sheet template; (3) draft and review content prior to dissemination across our website and social channels. Having SME's from within The HuT project developing these fact sheets is important, but we also want to recognize the learnings from the broader international community where information is available. Therefore, the fact sheets will also represent a way of signposting to both internal and external resources that can support advances in research and development for the specific challenge/theme being addressed. The cross-demonstrator identification of SME's and having these individuals as authors, also supports and strengthens collaboration across the project.

Our first Fact Sheet is being released in July/August 2024 and focuses on the design of early warning services, with a particular focus on Emergency Alerting in response to intense thunderstorms. This is an increasingly challenging issue for the DRR community as predictability, alert generation, action statement production and dissemination all need to take place within an exceptionally short window of time. This introduces scientific, technical and social challenges which need to be overcome to ensure success. We have specifically chosen to release this Fact Sheet in the summer because its theme is particularly topical and relevant in the European Summer when intense summer thunderstorms can result in impacts to society. Our second Fact Sheet is planned for January 2025 and will focus on the topic "Internet of Things" and its value and use in DRR activities.

5.4. Video Content

Ahead of the 2024 Annual Meeting which will take place in Switzerland in November 2024, we have been planning to conduct video interviews with consortium members from within the project. To ensure relevance we are aligning the interview topic with the [Early Warnings for All initiative](#) which was launched by the UN Secretary-General in March 2022.

We have identified a set of 3 questions which are being shared with selected individuals within the project and among the demonstrators. We will be asking individuals to prepare short responses to these questions, and we will then conduct short interviews, in-person where possible, during the annual meeting. We will then share these video outputs via the website and social media channels.

The core aim of these videos is to identify how The HuT project activities, and specifically work within the demonstrators, are working to support the global-scale Early Warnings for All initiative. It will also provide the project with an interim update on how members of the project see their progress, aligning with larger scale initiatives. This helps develop a baseline and ground the research being undertaken in The HuT with identified needs in the global context. We intend to repeat the interviews with similar questions towards the end of the project. This will enable us to better understand the benefits and value of the research within the broader global context.

6. Local outreach and engagement activities

Local outreach and engagement are largely managed at the demonstrator level. There are however engagement activities also taking place across the HuT work packages, but these are managed carefully and facilitated by the designated leads of each demonstrator. This is to ensure that relationships built by in-country researchers with their different stakeholders are not negatively impacted by external researchers (to the demonstrator research group) interfacing separately to the demonstrator research group. Engagement and outreach at the demonstrator scale is non-prescriptive (i.e. the project recognizes that the needs for outreach and engagement will be different in each demonstrator unique circumstance) and typically tailored to the needs of the demonstrator and its goals, but also to the stakeholders who are being engaged with.

Local outreach and engagement activities are however fed back up to the project through Communication, Dissemination and Engagement (CDE) local desks and recorded within a logbook on a bimonthly basis. ICONS promoted the creation of the local desks to oversee the local D&C strategy definition, including the identification of appropriate channels, messages and specific social media and communication formats to foster citizen engagement (even in addition to those already implemented at project level). The CDE local desks operate, under the guidance of WP6 leader, who are also as the main contact points to implement campaigns dedicated to local stakeholders and citizens' engagement, under the coordination of the DEM leader, facilitating the deployment of the citizens' and stakeholders' engagement strategy locally in a very effective and customized way.

Throughout the project to date, local activities organized within the demonstrator areas include:

- Multiple meetings and workshops with local stakeholders (Valencia, Monti Lattari, Vilnius, Schleswig, Fjords, Tisza, Ogliastra, Dorset, Berne)
- Education/training activities (Scientific week in local schools Val D'Aran, civil defense activity in Monti Lattari, serious games testing in Schleswig, participation to a summer school in Berne)
- Interviews, media articles and social media posts (Valencia, Monti Lattari, Schleswig, Fjords, Ogliastra, Berne)

7. ICONS Engagement Indexes

Engagement can be regarded as the state in which stakeholders interact actively with the project itself and its outcomes. The ability to assess the effectiveness of communication and engagement is therefore crucial.

To track and analyse stakeholders' engagement, ICONS has developed a methodology based on continuous monitoring of (i) the distribution of a project's content; and (ii) the engagement mechanisms of all project communication activities, across all the channels considered. This activity tracks the number of visualizations of and interactions with a project's content. The methodologies of the indexes mentioned earlier in various parts of the report are described in this section.

Outreach indicators. They assess the size of the audience reached by the content conveyed to strengthen target stakeholders' awareness. Outreach indicators are basic indices that on their own do not provide a complete picture of a project's communication effectiveness. They rather serve as a starting point for further analysis.

Engagement indicators. They help understand how effective a project content is in generating interest and boosting acceptance from target stakeholders. Engagement metrics measure if and how stakeholders engage with the content, via e.g. online interactions. They are a quite powerful tool for assessing the effectiveness of the communication campaigns performed.

ICONS studied a series of indices able to quantify the interest of a community in specific content. With specific reference to contents distribution, the following indices are to be accounted for:

- CEI, Community Engagement Index
- PEI, Publication Engagement Index
- WEI, Website Engagement Index
- SEI, Social Engagement Index

Community Engagement Index (CEI)

The Community Engagement Index (CEI) developed by ICONS is used to assess and evaluate the results and impacts of the project. The CEI is a function of the outreach and engagement indicators, and it is calculated as the ratio between total engagement and total outreach. It integrates all communication activities, both online and offline (i.e. publications, project website, social media, webinars, workshops/events, and other activities) into one single metric. Low values of the CEI indicate little interest by the target audience (compared to its outreach), while high values suggest high interest and engagement of the community.

To facilitate the readability, understanding and comparability of these indexes, ICONS normalized them to a range from 0 to 100. The closer the index is to 100, the better the engagement is. The definition of the optimal value used for normalization is based on all the EU projects managed by ICONS.

The figures below display the project's CEI and an overview on the project's general impacts per area. It is worth to highlight PEI's overperformance, with index over 100, a good outreach and a discrete engagement.

Figure 8: The HuT project's Community Engagement Index (CEI) and an overview of the project's general impact across the different engagement indices.

Publication Engagement Index (PEI)

The Publication Engagement Index (PEI) lets ICONS gauge, in a quantitative way, the actual engagement of people with the publications provided by The HuT project via the following channels: websites (project website and youris.com), social media, and media multipliers.

The index is expressed as a percentage, similar to how penetration rates are usually reported in market analysis reports, and can be calculated at different levels:

- by publication;
- by publication type (article, news release, press release, video, etc.).

Website Engagement Index (WEI)

The Website Engagement Index (WEI) quantifies the engagement of The Hut's website visitors with the contents published in its pages. Outreach is measured based on the total number of page views, while its engagement is gauged as the amount of time spent on these pages.

The index is expressed in percentage with a natural range between 0 and 1. Its value tends to be higher in comparison to PEI. In contrast to the engagement according to the publications, the engagement recorded on the website is based on the visitors' attention span, rather than the specific actions performed (i.e. downloads, shares).

Social Engagement Index (SEI)

The Social Engagement Index (SEI) measures the level of interest generated by all the social media posts made by The HuT project; it also represents the amount of engagement made between the social media users with the content present in these posts. This is calculated by finding the ratio between the outreach and engagement levels for each social media channel.

The SEI percentages vary depending on how these channels work. Twitter, for example, has a wider online community in comparison to LinkedIn. This explains the substantial level of outreach with respect to LinkedIn. It, however, falls behind with the level of engagement as a public Twitter account opens its doors to anyone, while a LinkedIn page provides more familiarity with its followers as they are committed to following the content shared by the page.

8. Monitoring

The impact of The HuT's communication and dissemination products is measured throughout the duration of the project. This is done by monitoring and studying products' engagement with their respective target audiences. Online media outreach, in particular, is calculated using a methodology that relies on automated tools that collect reliable statistics and data.

Data on the C&D products and selected channels are gathered using state-of-the-art monitoring tools, tracking the diffusion of the contents online, the visitors of the The Hut's website, the social media outreach, as well as the number of attendees at specific events.

The monitoring was moved to [Matomo](#) due to GDPR compliance reasons (for a certain period of time, Google Tag Manager was not GDPR compliant, reason why ICONS deemed it necessary to shift to another monitoring tool).

Matomo assesses the performance of the project website as well. It is used extensively to retrieve available data about the traffic (in terms of the number of views, sessions, and users' behaviour) and the audience it reaches out to.

Press and news releases and journalistic articles are monitored as well by calculating the outreach generated by the spontaneous take-ups of the Hut's content on websites and social media channels. This reporting activity will be done using available tools, social media analytics programs i.e. Twitter Analytics, LinkedIn Insights and data coming from external platforms and multipliers.

The outreach data collected will let us quantify the number of users reached through the project's C&D activities thereby becoming the key input to C&D indexes to measure the actual engagement of The Hut's community via the project contents delivered on the internet and social media.

